

ISSIQLIK TARQALISH TENGLAMASI UCHUN KOSHI MASALASI

Sharipova Madina Po‘latovna

Osiyo Xalqaro Universiteti

“Umumtexnik fanlar” kafedrası o‘qituvchisi

saripovamadina807.m@gmail.com

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada issiqlik tenglamasiga qo‘yilgan to‘g‘ri va teskari masalalarning umumlashgan yechimlarining to‘g‘riligi o‘rganilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: *Uzluksizlik, funksional qator, Fure koeffitsienti, tor tebranish tenglamasi.*

ANNOTATION

The dissertation “Non local boundary conditional direct and inverse problems in an unbounded domain for the heat propagation in three-dimensional space” is one of the important sections of mathematics. Interest in this field is determined by the theoretical significance if the obtained results and their practical applications.

Kirish

Matematik fizikaning juda ko‘p masalalarini xususiy hosilali tenglamalar ko‘rinishida tavsiflash mumkin. Bunday tavsivlashda unga mos bo‘lgan chegaraviy masalalar yechimini tabiiy aniqlash imkoniyati mavjud va shu bilan birga, ularni yechishga ma‘lum usullarni qo‘llash mumkin. Tabiatda uchraydigan jarayonlarni kasr tartibli tenglamalar aniqroq ifoda etadi.

Issiqlik tarqalish tenglamasi.

Koshi masalasi: Tekislikdagi $\Omega = \{(x, t) : 0 < x < l, 0 < t < T\}$ sohada bir jinsli

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = a^2 \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} \quad (a = \text{const}) \quad (1)$$

issiqlik tarqalish tenglamasining

$$u(x,0) = \varphi(x), \quad 0 \leq x \leq l \quad (2)$$

boshlang'ich va

$$u(0,t) = 0, \quad u(l,t) = 0, \quad 0 \leq t < T \quad (3)$$

bir jinsli chegaraviy shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi regulyar yechimi topilsin.

Ta'rif: (1) tenglamaning regulyar yoki klassik yechimi deb Ω sohada, tenglamada qatnashuvchi o'zining hosilalari bilan uzluksiz va tenglamani ayniyatga aylantiruvchi $u=u(x,y)$ funksiyaga aytiladi.

Aralash masalani o'zgaruvchilarni ajratish (yoki Furye) usuli bilan yechamiz.

Bu usulga asosan (1) tenglamaning yechimini

$$u(x,t) = X(x)T(t) \quad (4)$$

shaklda izlasak, quyidagi

$$X''(x) + \lambda X(x) = 0, \quad (5)$$

$$T'(x) + a^2 \lambda T(t) = 0 \quad (6)$$

ikkita oddiy differensial tenglama hosil bo'ladi, bunda $\lambda = \text{const}$. (4) ifoda va (3) chegaraviy shartlardan (5) tenglama uchun quyidagi

$$X(0) = X(l) = 0 \quad (7)$$

chegaraviy shartlar kelib chiqadi.

(5), (7) masala - xos son va xos funksiyalarni topish xaqidagi Shturm-Liuvill masalasi bo'lib, u tor tebranish tenglamasi uchun aralash masalani yechishda ham qurilgan edi.

Bu masalaning xos sonlari $\lambda_n = \left(\frac{\pi n}{l}\right)^2$, $(n = 1, 2, \dots)$, bu xos sonlarga mos

trivial bo'lmagan xos funksiyalari $X_n(x) = \sin \frac{\pi n}{l} x$ ko'rinishda ekanligini

aniqlagan edik. $\lambda = \lambda_n$ bo'lganda (6) tenglamaning umumiy yechimi

$$T_n(t) = a_n e^{-(a\pi n/l)^2 t}$$

ko'rinishga ega bo'lib, (1.2.4) tenglikka asosan

$$U_n(x,t) = X_n(x)T_n(t) = a_n e^{-\left(\frac{\pi n a}{l}\right)^2 t} \sin \frac{\pi n}{l} x$$

funksiyalar (a_n -ixtiyoriy, o'zgarimas sonlar) (1) tenglamani va (3) chegaraviy shartni qanoatlantiradi. Tenglama bir jinsli bo'lgani uchun bu yechimlar yig'indisi yana yechim bo'ladi. Shuning uchun (1) tenglamaning (2), (3) shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi yechimini

$$u(x,t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n e^{-\left(\frac{\pi n a}{l}\right)^2 t} \sin \frac{\pi n}{l} x \quad (8)$$

qator ko'rinishida izlaymiz. Agar (8) Funktsional qator va uning t bo'yicha birinchi, x bo'yicha ikkinchi tartibli hosilalari tekis yaqinlashuvchi bo'lsa, u holda bum qator yig'indisi (1) tenglamani va (3) chegaraviy shartlarni qanoatlantiradi. Boshlang'ich shartni ham qanoatlantirishini talab qilsak,

$$u(x,0) = \varphi(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n \sin \frac{\pi n}{l} x$$

tenglikka ega bo'lamiz. Bu tenglikni $\varphi(x)$ funksiyaning $(0,l)$ oraliqdagi sinuslar bo'yicha Fure qatoriga yoyilmasi desak, u holda a_n Fure koeffitsienti bo'lib,

$$a_n = \frac{2}{l} \int_0^l \varphi(x) \sin \frac{\pi n}{l} x dx \quad (9)$$

formula bo'yicha topiladi.

(9) tenglikka asosan (1)-(3) masalaning (8) yechimini quyidagi ko'rinishda yozish mumkin

$$u(x,t) = \int_0^l G(x,y,t) \varphi(y) dy, \quad (10)$$

bu yerda

$$G(x,y,t) = \frac{2}{l} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\left(\frac{\pi n a}{l}\right)^2 t} \sin \frac{\pi n}{l} x \sin \frac{\pi n}{l} y.$$

Bu funksiya oniy manbaning ta'sir funksiyasi deyiladi.

1- Teorema. Agar $[0,1]$ kesmada $\varphi(x)$ funksiya

1. uzluksiz;
2. bo'lakli-uzluksiz hosilaga ega va
3. $\varphi(0)=\varphi(1)=0$

shartni qanoatlantirsa, u holda (8) qator aralash masalaning $\bar{\Omega}$ da uzluksiz va cheksiz differensiallanuvchi yechimi bo'ladi.

(2) funksiya aralash masalaning yechimi bo'lishi uchun, (2) boshlang'ich shartda berilgan $\varphi(x)$ funksiya uzluksiz, bo'lakli silliq va boshlang'ich hamda chegaraviy shartlarning moslashganlik shartiga ($\varphi(0)=\varphi(1)=0$) bo'ysunishi kerak. Lekin $\varphi(x)$ funksiyaning uzluksizligi va moslashganlik shartini qanoatlantirishi amaliyot uchun og'ir shartdir.

Masalan, $U_0 = const$ temperaturagacha isitilgan va chetlarida nol temperaturaga ega bo'lgan, soviyotgan sterjenda issiqlik tarqalish masalasida, boshlang'ich va chegaraviy shartlarning moslashganlik sharti bajarilmaydi, ya'ni $\varphi(0)=\varphi(1)=0=U_0 \neq 0$. Bu holda quyidagi teorema o'rinalidir.

2- Teorema. Agar $[0,1]$ kesmada $\varphi(x)$ funksiya bo'lakli-uzluksiz (I - tur uzilishlarga ega) bo'lsa, u holda (10) funksiya:

- 1) Ω sohada (1) tenglamasining yechimi bo'ladi;
- 2) $\bar{\Omega} = \{(x,t) : 0 \leq x \leq l, 0 \leq t \leq T\}$ sohada chegaralangan;
- 3) (3) chegaraviy shartlarni qanoatlantiradi;
- 4) $t=0$ da $\varphi(x)$ funksiyaning uzluksiz nuqtalarida uzluksiz va $u(x,0)=\varphi(x)$

bo'ladi.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR RO'YXATI

1. Sharipova, M. P. L. (2023). CAPUTA MA'NOSIDA KASR TARTIBLI HOSILALAR VA UNI HISOBLASH USULLARI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(9), 360-365.
2. Sharipova, M. P. (2023). MAXSUS SOHALARDA KARLEMAN MATRITSASI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(10), 137-141.

3. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). APPROXIMATION OF FUNCTIONS WITH COEFFICIENTS. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(9), 135–138.
4. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). Applications of the double integral to mechanical problems. *International journal of sciearchers*, 2(2), 101-103.
5. Sharipova, M. P. L. (2023). FINDING THE MAXIMUM AND MINIMUM VALUE OF A FUNCTION ON A SEGMENT. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(9), 245-248.
6. Sharipova, M. P. (2023). FUNKSIYALARNI KOEFFITSIENTLAR ORQALI FUNKSIYALARNI YAKINLASHTIRISH HAQIDA MA'LUMOTLAR. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(34), 102–110.
7. Sharipova, M. (2023, December). RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN STRAIGHT LINES AND PLANES IN SPACE. In *Международная конференция академических наук* (Vol. 2, No. 12, pp. 60-66).
8. Sharipova, M. (2023). FRACTIONAL DERIVATIVES. *Академические исследования в современной науке*, 2(27), 106-113.
9. Sharipova, M. (2023). CORRECT PLACED AND CORRECT NOT PLACED ISSUES. *Models and methods in modern science*, 2(13), 115-121.
10. Sharipova, M. (2023). HEAT SPREAD EQUATION. *Инновационные исследования в науке*, 2(12), 50-56.
11. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). HIGH MATH SCORE AND INTERVAL ASSESSMENT. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(10), 420–424.
12. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). IN HIGHER MATHEMATICS, THE EXTREMUM OF A MULTIVARIABLE FUNCTION. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(10), 425–429.
13. Xamroyevna, B. M. (2023). ORGANIZM TO 'QIMALARINING ZICHLIGINI ANIQLASH. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(34), 50-58.
14. Mukhtaram Bobokulova Khamroyevna. (2023). Radiation Protection. Dosimetry . *Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science*, 4(6), 134-139.
15. Bobokulova, M. K. (2023). IMPORTANCE OF FIBER OPTIC DEVICES IN MEDICINE. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 3(5), 212-216.
16. Khamroyevna, M. B. (2023). PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF BIOLOGICAL MEMBRANES, BIOPHYSICAL MECHANISMS OF MOVEMENT OF SUBSTANCES IN THE MEMBRANE. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 3(5), 217-221.

17. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). BETA FUNKSIYA XOSSALARI VA BU FUNKSIYA YORDAMIDA TURLI MASALALARNI YECHISH. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(34), 66-76.

18. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). SOLVING THE INVERSE PROBLEM OF FINDING THE SOURCE FUNCTION IN FRACTIONAL ORDER EQUATIONS. *International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development*, 10(12).

19. Latipova, S. S. (2023). SOLVING THE INVERSE PROBLEM OF FINDING THE SOURCE FUNCTION IN FRACTIONAL ORDER EQUATIONS. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 1(10), 13-23.

20. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). HEAT PHYSICAL MEANING AND ORIGIN OF DIFFUSION EQUATIONS. *International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development*, 10(12).

21. daughter Latipova, S. S. (2023). HEAT PHYSICAL MEANING AND ORIGIN OF DIFFUSION EQUATIONS. *World of Scientific news in Science*, 1(2), 163-176.

22. Shahnoza, L. (2023, March). KASR TARTIBLI TENGLAMALARDA MANBA VA BOSHLANG'ICH FUNKSIYANI ANIQLASH BO'YICHA TESKARI MASALALAR. In " *Conference on Universal Science Research 2023*" (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 8-10).

23. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). RIMAN-LUIVILL KASR TARTIBLI INTEGRALI VA HOSILASIGA OID AYRIM MASALALARNING ISHLANISHI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(12), 216-220.

24. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). MITTAG-LIFFLER FUNKSIYASI VA UNI HISOBLASH USULLARI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(9), 238-244.

25. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). KASR TARTIBLI HOSILA TUSHUNCHASI. *SCHOLAR*, 1(31), 263-269.

26. Муродов, О. Т. (2023). РАЗРАБОТКА АВТОМАТИЗИРОВАННОЙ СИСТЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ТЕМПЕРАТУРЫ И ВЛАЖНОСТИ В ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННЫХ КОМНАТ. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(26), 91-95.

27. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). ZAMONAVIY TA'LIMDA AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYALARI VA ULARNI QO'LLASH USUL VA VOSITALARI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(10), 481-486.

28. Murodov, O. T. (2023). INFORMATIKA FANINI O'QITISHDA YANGI INNOVATSION USULLARDAN FOYDALANISH METODIKASI. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(34), 130-139.

29. qizi Sharopova, M. M. (2023). RSA VA EL-GAMAL OCHIQ KALITLI SHIFRLASH ALGORITMI ASOSIDA ELEKTRON RAQMLI IMZOLARI. RSA

OCHIQ KALITLI SHIFRLASH ALGORITMI ASOSIDAGI ELEKTRON RAQAMLI IMZO. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(10), 316-319.

30. Sharopova, M. M. qizi . (2023). JAVA TILI YORDAMIDA OB'EKTGA YUNALTIRILGAN DASTURLASH ASOSLARI BILAN TANISHISH. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(34), 111–119.

31. Sharopova, M. (2023). CHOOSE: COMPOSITION OR INHERITANCE. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 2(13), 96-102.

32. Sharopova, M. (2023). JAVA PROGRAMMING IN THE LANGUAGE HERITAGE TO DO SYNTAX. *Current approaches and new research in modern sciences*, 2(12), 82-87.

33. Sharopova, M. (2023). ARRAY AND ARRAYS INSTALLATION. *Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences*, 2(12), 102-107.

34. Sharopova, M. (2023). CLASSES AGAIN APPLY. *Solution of social problems in management and economy*, 2(13), 106-111.

35. qizi Sharopova, M. M. (2023). INTRODUCING" PROGRAM CONTROL OPERATORS" IN THE JAVA PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 3(5), 222-231.

36. qizi Sharopova, M. M. (2023). Working with folders in the JAVA programming language. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 3(5), 232-236.

37. Behruz Ulugbek og, Q. (2023). TECHNOLOGY AND MEDICINE: A DYNAMIC PARTNERSHIP. *International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development*, 10(11).

38. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g', Q. li.(2023). Mobil ilovalar va ularni bajarish jarayoni. *Xalqaro ilmiy tadqiqotchilar jurnali* , 2 (2).

39. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g', Q. (2023). SUN'IY NERV TIZIMLARIDAN MODELLASHDA FOYDALANISH. *Fan va texnologiyaning ko'p tarmoqli jurnali* , 3 (5), 269-273.

40. Behruz Ulug'bek og', Q. (2023). TEXNOLOGIYA VA TIBBIYOT: DINAMIK HAMKORLIK. *Tadqiqot va ishlanmalar bo'yicha xalqaro multidisipliner jurnali* , 10 (11).

41. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Nurboyev, O. (2023). FIZIKA FANINING BO 'LIMLARINING RIVOJLANISHDAGIDAGI ASOSIY AHAMIYATI. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(33), 162-167.

42. Jurakulov, S. Z., & Nurboyev, O. (2023). FIZIKA FANINING BO 'LIMLARINING RIVOJLANISHDAGIDAGI ASOSIY AHAMIYATI. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(33), 162-167.

43. Jurakulov, S. (2023). IMPACT OF THE MINING INDUSTRY ON PEOPLE AND THE ENVIRONMENT. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 2(21), 143-150.
44. Jurakulov, S. (2023). CHANGES IN LANGUAGE DUE TO NEW PHYSICS. Models and methods in modern science, 2(13), 77-87.
45. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). СОЗДАНИЕ ПРОГРАММЫ ДЛЯ ИМИТАЦИИ ШИФРОВАНИЯ МАШИНЫ ENIGMA НА ЯЗЫКЕ PYTHON. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 317-323.
46. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). STUDY THE PSYCHOLOGY OF PROGRAMMERS. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(10), 563-568.
47. Tursunov, B. J., & Allanazarov, G. O. (2019). Perspektivnye tehnologii proizvodstva po uluchsheniyu kachestva benzina. *Theory and practice of contemporary science*, 3(45), 305-308.
48. Турсунов, Б. Ж., & Алланазаров, Г. О. (2019). Перспективные технологии производства по улучшению качества бензина. *Теория и практика современной науки*, (3 (45)), 305-308.
49. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). Analysis of Concepts About the Effect of an Explosion in Solid Wednesday. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(10), 296-304.
50. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). Methods of Control of Explosion Energy Distribution in Rocks. *Intersections of Faith and Culture: American Journal of Religious and Cultural Studies (2993-2599)*, 1(10), 108-117.
51. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). WASTE-FREE TECHNOLOGY FOR ENRICHMENT OF PURIFIC COPPER-ZINC ORE. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(9), 288-293.
52. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). ANALYSIS OF MODERN METHODS FOR OIL SLUDGE PROCESSING. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(9), 280-287.
53. Jumaev, K., & Tursunov, B. (2022, December). Environmentally friendly technology for obtaining fuel briquettes from oil waste. In *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* (Vol. 1112, No. 1, p. 012005). IOP Publishing.
54. Ахмедова, О. Б., Турсунов, Б. Ж., & угли Худойбердиев, Н. Н. (2022). Анализ физико-химических свойств нефтешламов Бухарского НПЗ и рациональные способы их утилизации. *Science and Education*, 3(6), 495-507.
55. Турсунов, Б. Д. (2016). Анализ и выявление путей совершенствования процессов горного дела. *Молодой ученый*, (23), 105-106.